

RealWorld Systems

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Addendum:
Review of Host Group Service Models in Ontario

Citizenship and Immigration Canada

Ontario Settlement Directorate

Prepared by

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Report

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ADDENDUM: REVIEW OF HOST GROUP SERVICE MODELS IN ONTARIO

1. INTRODUCTION

This is the addendum to the report entitled "Review of Host Group Service Models in Ontario". The addendum includes a detailed description of the methodology, with interview protocols, a spreadsheet listing the names of the agencies offering Host group models with details of the group model characteristics, and charts summarizing some of the spreadsheet data.

For the main report, contact Citizenship and Immigration Canada, Ontario Region, or RealWorld Systems. Both reports will be posted on settlement.org in May 2005.

2. METHODOLOGY

There were four stages to the review:

1. Identifying and describing all of the Host group models that are currently being provided;
2. Analysing the models that demonstrate the most potential in terms of their effectiveness;
3. Synthesizing the data and developing recommendations;
4. Consulting with CIC and service providers

To identify group models, we interviewed staff from each of the 19 Ontario Host agencies, reviewed their CIC files, visited six agencies and participated in several group activities, and reviewed the literature on settlement and integration. Agencies were consulted throughout the process. An advisory committee included agency staff, and preliminary results were presented and discussed at a national Host conference workshop on February 17 before the final consultation with Ontario Host agencies on March 2 (see notes from the meeting below).

The Advisory Committee to this project consisted of Elisete Bettencourt, Lynn Murrell, Jackie Smith and Eva Goodyer from Citizenship and Immigration Canada, and representatives from four service provider organizations: Arsim Aliu from Settlement and Integration Services Organization (SISO) in Hamilton, Mira Malidzanovic from the Kitchener-Waterloo Reception Centre, Sally Spencer from Youth Assisting Youth in Toronto and Lucila Spigelblatt from Catholic Immigration Centre in Ottawa.

Following is a detailed description of the methodology.

2.1. Identify and describe the Host group models currently provided

Key assessment questions: *What group activities are being delivered throughout the region? How are the various group models intended to operate? How are they actually operating? Can the various group models be classified or categorized in ways that might lead to mechanisms for ongoing service delivery improvement?*

- *Review background documents*

RealWorld Systems conducted a review of background documents to ensure that the evaluation team has a good understanding of the Host program and its various forms of delivery. Background document review provided information that addressed some of the evaluation questions, reducing the need for more time-consuming and expensive data collection efforts. Among the background documents were the final report from the 2000 Host evaluation (referenced in the main report), English Conversation Circle guidelines (attached in this report) and Host program terms of reference.

- *Review of agency files at CIC*

A file review of all HOST-funded agencies was conducted in the early stages of the project. The goals of the file review were:

- to describe each Host program in sufficient detail as to orient the interviewer; and,
- to begin to profile the group models in use across the province.

This file review did not assess the quality or accuracy of the file and its contents – it merely sought to extract useful information that would reduce duplication (i.e., asking agencies for information that was already in their files) and would guide the interviewer (by providing an organizational context).

The file review process included scanning each file, with particular attention paid to the following documents (if available in the file):

- Schedule 1 for 2004-2005 (focus on targets for the upcoming year);
- Monthly Statistical Reports prepared by the agencies;
- Narrative reports that accompanied the Monthly Statistical Reports ;
- Assessment and Recommendation for Approval/Refusal (Ontario Region 2004-2005);
- Host Application Form (2004-2005); and,
- Promotional and evaluation materials.

Pertinent information about the Host program was extracted into an Excel spreadsheet. Examples of selected information include Host program budget, CIC settlement officer, minimum number of matchers, numbers of GARs ad PSRs, number of program promotion sessions, # of volunteers recruited / matched, # of ECCs, Host staffing complement. Additional attention was paid to descriptions of Host group models as well as volunteer management activities.

The data were then compiled into an Agency interview protocol that included a statistical profile of the Host program (incorporating elements of the above documents), as well as brief descriptions of Host groups underway. All information, both our interview notes

and the material drawn from the files, was provided to the agency for approval after the interview process.

- *Meetings with CIC staff*

RealWorld Systems facilitated a meeting with CIC staff, followed up with phone interviews, in order to gather their input and insights on the various Host group models being delivered throughout the Ontario region and to identify promising practices.

- *Conduct telephone interviews with agencies*

RealWorld Systems conducted structured and lengthy telephone interviews with staff at all nineteen of the agencies currently delivering Host services. Where necessary, we spoke to more than one staff person per agency. These interviews identified or confirmed the types of group models being delivered, and delved in some depth into the processes that go into their group services. We were trying to gather enough information about the models that we could describe the key components and fit the models into meaningful categories for analysis. In addition, the interviews included a reputational survey (described below) in order to identify the most effective group practices.

All of the 19 agencies receiving Host funding in 2004/2005 were interviewed for this study. Only 15 of them were currently providing Host groups in 2004, and they are listed in the attached spreadsheet.

2.2. Analyse the most promising Host group models

Key assessment questions: *What are the benefits and challenges to Host volunteers, clients and agencies? What models appear most promising and why? What are the best ways to replicate effective service delivery throughout the region within existing Service Provider Organization (SPO) budgets?*

- *Identify potential best practices, challenges and benefits*

- Conduct reputational survey

During the meetings with CIC staff and phone interviews with agencies, RealWorld Systems asked participants to name successful models or other Host agencies that they think are particularly effective. These agencies or models were flagged for deeper assessment, including site visits.

- Mine existing qualitative data sources

RealWorld Systems used the extensive data collected during its evaluation of the ISAP & Host Programs in 2002-2003 as well as data collected from the Results Based Management workshops and logic model development it conducted earlier in 2004. Specifically, mined the qualitative interview data collected from 101 immigrants and refugees for Host related information, including client satisfaction and effective practice evidence, to supplement client interview data. We also

mined the notes of the RBM Host workshops across Canada to identify issues related to Host group models. This approach provided the evaluation team with data that has more depth and richness than it would otherwise have access to.

- Conduct agency site visits

RealWorld Systems conducted six agency site visits with agencies identified in the earlier phase of the project as having promising group models. RealWorld Systems spent approximately one day at each of the six agencies attending groups and interviewing agency staff, volunteers and newcomers. The site visit protocol is attached below. The agencies visited were:

- CultureLink in Toronto
- Folk Arts Council of St Catherines
- Multicultural Council of Windsor & Essex
- Settlement and Integration Services Organization (SISO) in Hamilton
- YMCA of Kitchener-Waterloo
- Youth Assisting Youth in Toronto

NOTE: We believe that for the purposes of this particular evaluation, written surveys are not an effective way to collect feedback for several reasons, including variation in written language proficiency, anxiety about the reasons for the survey, and the challenges in getting meaningful answers about effectiveness. In-depth interviews and site visits, even when restricted to a small carefully selected sample, supplemented by other data such as agency files and statistics, reveal a great deal about potentially effective services.

- *Summarize and review service statistics (planned but unable to do)*

RealWorld Systems had intended to analyse program administrative data collected through the Immigration Contribution Accountability Management System (iCAMS). Unfortunately, iCAMS data were not yet available from Citizenship and Immigration Canada.

- *Review literature*

RealWorld Systems reviewed the literature, including preliminary results from the Longitudinal Survey of Immigrants to Canada, for evidence of effectiveness of Host group service models and sources that identify and describe effective and efficient settlement programs in Canada or elsewhere for comparison with CIC Ontario programs. A key data source and starting point for this review were the results of two literature scans that RealWorld Systems carried out during the ISAP and Host Evaluation in 2002, and during the revision of CIC's settlement evaluation framework in 2004.

2.3. Developing conclusions and recommendations

As RealWorld Systems synthesized and analyzed the data collected from the various channels described above, we checked our emerging conclusions with CIC staff and Host agencies in a series of phone calls and meetings to test their credibility and usefulness. RealWorld Systems uses this back-and-forth process in all of our evaluations to build consensus and identify areas of risk. When we received feedback on concerns, we would discuss the issue with CIC and agency stakeholders until a consensus emerged.

2.4. Taking guidance from an Advisory Committee

RealWorld Systems worked with an advisory committee comprising CIC staff and representatives from four service providers. The committee reviewed and approved the methodology, interview protocols and initial conclusions and recommendations.

The advisory committee members were:

- Elisete Bettencourt, CIC (initial project lead)
- Lynn Murrell, CIC (replacing Elisete as project lead)
- Jackie Smith, CIC
- Eva Goodyer, CIC
- Arsim Aliu from Settlement and Integration Services Organization (SISO) in Hamilton
- Mira Malidzanovic from the Kitchener-Waterloo Reception Centre
- Sally Spencer from Youth Assisting Youth in Toronto
- Lucila Spigelblatt from Catholic Immigration Centre in Ottawa

2.5 Consulting with Host Service Providers

Finally, RealWorld Systems presented draft conclusions and recommendations at two agency consultations. First, we held a workshop at the National Host Conference on February 17 to participants from national Host agencies and CIC staff. Based on feedback from that workshop, we presented revised conclusions to an Ontario Host consultation on March 2, at which thirteen agencies attended. The final report incorporates feedback from both consultations.

The March 2 meeting was held at the Citizenship and Immigration Canada offices in Toronto from noon to 4:30pm. The results of the review were presented by Gillian Kerr and Anne Simard in PowerPoint and then Gillian Kerr facilitated an open discussion.

The participants (listed below) discussed and generally approved the recommendations as listed in the final report. Several issues and points were raised that were subsequently incorporated into the final paper. Major issues include:

- Community engagement approaches for refugees may be a bad idea if refugees are met in Toronto by representatives of the group that they fled. Refugees must feel safe and secure in initial stages of settlement; matching them with local members of their own ethnocultural communities is risky and must be handled carefully.
- Participants formally voted to accept the recommendation that ,“The core objective for Host groups should be defined as: **To help newcomers link to diverse social networks in the host community**. Other objectives, such as English practice, should be secondary.” The initial recommendation made by RealWorld Systems was that the primary objective for the entire Host program should be helping newcomers link to diverse social networks. However, some participants pointed out that the core objective of the one-to-one matches might be somewhat different, and that more study was needed. All agreed that Host’s core objective should not be language learning.
- Another strong point was that Host should not devalue one-to-one matches. The current review only studied Host group models, and did not compare the relative value of groups vs. 1-1 matches.
- There were many questions about how indicators would be defined and tested. Agencies pointed out that indicators should be validated against outcomes, should use sampling approaches to save costs, and should be flexible enough to be appropriate in various communities.
- There is a need for volunteer training around building networks.
- Host services may need to recruit more professional volunteers for mentoring and helping newcomers join relevant networks. How should Host attract volunteers from the corporate and business world?

Participants

Host Service Providers:

Mira Jankovic, Halton Multicultural Council, Oakville
Sally Spencer, Youth Assisting Youth, Toronto
Arsim Aliu, SISO Hamilton
Safia Shire, CultureLink, Toronto

Joyce David, Kingston and District Immigrant Services (KDIS)
Malika Mounir, Folk Arts Council, St. Catherines
Marisa Gelfusa, Centre Francophone de Toronto
Doug Ryan
Siva Appiuh
Rosanna McLeod
Lynn Murrell
Richard Lecours
Eva Goodyer
Shana Getty
Karen Cecco
Liz Dobrzanski
Christine Charbonneau
Marcela Diaz, Multicultural Council of Windsor and Essex
Linda Woodbeck, Thunder Bay Multicultural Association
Luisa Fernanda vega, New Canadians Centre Peterborough
Lucila Spigelblatt, Catholic Immigration Centre, Ottawa
Rahma Elmi, KW YMCA Cross Cultural and Community Services
Maria Alvarez, KW YMCA Cross Cultural and Community Services
Stephen Lam, Catholic Community Services of York Region

CIC Staff

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Lynn Murrell
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Eva Goodyer
Shana Getty
Karen Cecco
Liz Dobrzanski
Christine Charbonneau

3. HOST AGENCY INTERVIEW PROTOCOL – GROUP MODELS

Introduction:

As you know, we are studying Host group models for CIC Ontario Region. We are trying to find out what kinds of group Host programs are being offered in Ontario, to describe the different models, and to share information about what is working well.

Do you have any concerns or hopes about this study?

Consent:

I will be taking detailed notes on our conversation, and will send you the notes of this interview so you can make corrections or changes. The information in the notes may be shared with CIC and other agencies in the following ways, so it's important that you make sure we have captured your responses correctly:

- We may be quoting excerpts of agency comments in the final report, along with the agency's name or city. It's often important to know whether a comment relates to Toronto or Thunder Bay, for example.
- We want to collect descriptions of best practices to share with the sector. For example, we may list some agencies that have especially good outreach or recruitment processes.
- And of course we will summarize general themes that come up in the interviews.

The goal of this study is information sharing, so it is not a confidential process. If you decide that you don't want me to share some of the information that we've covered, or if you want to make anonymous statements, let me know and I can remove those comments from the notes. Remember that you can also make corrections to the interview notes when we send them to you.

At the end of our project, we will have a meeting with all HOST providers to share our findings, present our recommendations, and get your feedback. We expect this will take place early in 2005.

Thanks very much. Here are the questions. Feel free to skip back to previous questions if you think of more detail you want to add. This is totally open-ended.

SECTION 1: REVIEW OF AGENCY PROFILE

1. We have sent you a document that summarizes your HOST program, based on information drawn from CIC's files. Did you receive it?
2. Some of this information will be included in the final report as part of the information sharing. After this interview, I will revise it based on your input. This final version will be sent to you by email. Do you have any changes at this point? *[NOTE: We*

can include verbal changes in the notes we send for their review. If agency wants to work on the profile and email in changes, especially to statistical report, it must be in by November 30.]

SECTION 2: AGENCY'S USE OF GROUP MODELS

3. **Does your agency provide any group activities for HOST clients?** [PROBE: In your HOST program, does anything else happen besides one-to-one matches? Do your clients ever get together in a group? What do they do?] [Refer to agency profile and ask about specific group models that are described there, e.g., "I see that you're providing x and x. Could you give me more detail about them...."]

If NO: Skip to question 28

If YES, for EACH model ask questions 2 through 25:

AN OVERALL VIEW OF THE GROUP ACTIVITY:

4. How do you refer to the group activities – what do you call it? (for example, English Conversation Circles).
5. How long have you been delivering these group activities? (When did you start? Get response in months or years and note if it is a pilot).
6. Does your agency work with any other organizations (partners) to deliver this group activity? [PROBE: does any other organizations help with recruitment, promotion, activities, etc.]. If so, who are they and what do they contribute? Has the partnership been successful?
7. How many groups are active for this activity at present? Is that typical?
8. Does this activity target a *specific* client population? If so, how would you describe that population? [PROBE: Youth, Children? Seniors? Refugees? Specific type of Refugee? Professionals? A specific ethnic group?, etc.]
9. How long is each group that is formed expected to remain together? (3, 6, 8, 12 months or other – specify).
10. What kinds of activities are suggested by your agency for the group? **Where** do activities take place? – in parks, libraries, at volunteers' homes, etc.?)
11. Does the agency fund or facilitate any of these activities or portions of these activities (such as paying for transportation, providing or paying for daycare, etc.) for this group? Where is the funding coming from? What other resources, in-kind donations, or partnerships are used to cover costs for Host activities?
12. What are the hoped-for outcomes for this activity? (PROBE: Using the intermediate outcomes on the HOST Logic Model see if you can find the best fit for this model – welcome, social networks, language, access to services, client goal achievement).

A LOOK AT A SINGLE GROUP FOR THIS ACTIVITY

13. How many clients participate in each group for this activity? [PROBE: Do they have a specific demographic makeup? Are they all of similar ethnic background? Mixed? Same age? Same values?, etc.)
14. How many volunteers participate in each group for this activity?
15. How often are they expected to meet together? How long is each group session or activity expected to last (1, 2, 3 or more hours)?
16. What are their respective roles? (PROBE: What are clients expected to do? How is this communicated?)
17. Are specific objectives for the groups ever set? (PROBE: What kinds of objectives? When? How? If the hoped-for outcome was client goal achievement were the goals specified at the outset?)
18. What goes on during a typical group session? (PROBE: If ECC, how is it conducted? If homework club, how is it conducted? We're trying to find out what characteristics best define a group session for this activity and will later relate it to the hoped-for outcomes.)

REGARDING MODEL SPECIFIC AGENCY ACTIVITIES:

Outreach Activities

19. What kinds of promotional and outreach efforts are made for this group activity (for volunteers specifically, for participants/clients?)
20. Of all these outreach activities, which work best for volunteers? For participants?

Volunteer Management

21. How do you screen and select volunteers for this group activity?
22. How do you provide training and/or orientation to volunteers for this group activity? [PROBE about the training approach, e.g., monthly 3-hour session, session for all volunteers, session that is specific to this group activity]
23. What does volunteer training entail [If their target population is refugees do they include PTSD awareness training? If their target population is youth do they include anything specific? Are volunteers taught about the various services available in the community so that they refer clients?]
24. How are client assessments handled for this group activity? If not, model specific what assessment criteria is used to point them to this particular model?
25. How are the group activities monitored and supported? [PROBE: Is there open and ongoing communication between the HOST coordinator and the volunteer? What do they do if they need help or advice? How are they expected to escalate the problems?]
26. What skills and educational background does the HOST coordinator in your agency have? [PROBE: Is this the same as other Host staff]

27. What kind of training and skills do you think are important for coordinating HOST programs?

EVALUATION

28. What would indicate a successful group under this model?
29. What would indicate an unsuccessful group under this model?
30. How do you evaluate the success of this activity? How do you assess the outcomes?

AFTER ALL GROUP ACTIVITIES HAVE BEEN EXPLORED:

31. Of all the group models we've discussed, which do you think is the most effective? Why? How could that model be improved in terms of effectiveness?
32. Of all the group models we've discussed, which do you think is the most efficient? (or efficiently run) Why? How could that model be improved in terms of efficiency?
33. What are the benefits of groups generally as compared to one-to-one matches? [PROBE: Do you use them to train volunteers?]

IF AGENCY DOES NOT DELIVER HOST GROUP ACTIVITIES, ASK Q28 & Q29:

34. Why don't you offer any HOST groups? OR Why are group activities not part of your HOST program?
35. Under what conditions would you consider offering them? Is there any one-on-one model that might translate well to groups?

SECTION 3: GROUP MODELS FOR HOST

36. What are some of the benefits and strengths of group models compared to the one-to-one matching HOST approach?

Is it more appropriate for certain target audiences (e.g., adults, seniors, youth, children) or certain activities?

37. What are some possible weaknesses of HOST group models? [PROBE: Some people have suggested that they are too structured and top-down, with HOSTS having more power than newcomers.]
38. Are there any agencies that do a good job with group activities for newcomers? Any good ideas or HOST models that we should know about?

Are any HOST group models especially effective or promising? Which ones? They might be offered by other agencies or countries, or even outside the HOST program. Why do you think they are effective?

SECTION 4: WRAP-UP

39. We've talked about a lot of what you've been doing. What practices do you think you're exceptionally good at? What would you like to share with your peers or CIC?

40. Are there any other challenges that you face in the HOST program that we should be considering? Is there anything else about HOST that is not specifically related to group activities but which you'd like to share?
41. What are the most important questions about HOST group models? What does the sector or CIC need to find out/investigate? [For example, what are the best volunteer recruitment/screening processes, how to serve refugees more effectively]
42. Is there anything else – apart from additional money – that would be helpful to make a difference?
43. Are there any other group activities for newcomers that you think would fit within HOST or that HOST should be considering?
44. What information should we looking at in our study? What recommendations do you hope will come out of this?

CLOSING

We've covered all the official questions I have. Did you want to add any other comments?

Do you have any questions about the study?

If any questions occur to you later you can contact either Gillian Kerr or Elisete Bettencourt. Would you like their contact information? (Gillian – 888-596-5290, ext. 11, gkerr@realworldsystems.net or Elisete – 416-952-0905 or Elisete.Bettencourt@cic.gc.ca)

Thanks very much for your time.

3. SITE VISIT PROTOCOL

Thank you for allowing us to find out more about your Host group activities. As you know, we selected your agency because we thought that your Host group services were among the most promising models being offered in Ontario. This study, funded by CIC, is not going to evaluate your services. Rather, we are exploring your group models to share your insights, experiences, and knowledge with other agencies and CIC staff.

We understand that January may be a bad time for a visit; clients may be discouraged by poor weather, and most groups are just in start-up phase. And some of the programs we are interested in are only provided in the summer.

Nevertheless, we would like to discuss with you any concerns or issues that you may have around the timelines and consider these in our analysis. We would like to plan our visits so that we can learn as much as possible without inconveniencing you or your clients and volunteers more than we absolutely have to while still meeting our March 31, 2005 deadline for CIC.

Basically, we want to:

- Read background material on your groups, as well as any evaluations you have done in the past few years
- Observe one or two group activities
- Talk to a few of your group clients and volunteers

Some of you provide Host services with a partner, such as a school, and may need permission from them. One of us will talk to you about how to deal with this situation. We have also received some feedback from our advisory committee, which includes agency representatives. They have suggested that in explaining our presence to partners and group members we should be regarded in the same way as partners (in that we represent CIC, which is a partner) or external resource people who come to your group sessions. (In fact, if you wanted we could give a small presentation/seminar on a topic like how the Canadian government is trying to improve how newcomers are served. If you like this idea, we could figure out a topic that might interest your groups.) We are also open to any suggestions that you may have to speed up the process and/or make it more acceptable to your partners. We would be happy to talk to them if you thought it would be helpful.

PLANNING FOR THE SITE VISIT:

3.1. Preparation: Review of supporting documentation for the group activity

The first step of our visit is to review existing background documents before we arrive at the agency. Please do not write or prepare any materials for us – we are just interested in documents that you have already developed for your own use.

Background documents on the agency's group activity:

We would like to see any existing documentation about the group activity or activities that we are observing, including:

- outline or schedule of activities (e.g., for a structured group that has specific topics);
- explanation of the functioning of the group (e.g., rules, expectations);
- volunteer job description;
- participant job description or role description;
- any other supporting documentation that the agency thinks would be helpful to the consultant. If you are not sure what would be helpful, or if it is a lot of material, we can look at it during the visit and decide together whether we should make copies. Examples of 'other supporting documentation' could include training materials, worksheets, evaluation reports, presentations and so on.

Background documents on the agency's Host program:

We would like to see your current evaluation forms and any recent evaluation reports for the Host program as a whole, if you have them. The consultants would be happy to sign your agency's confidentiality agreement if you wish. Documents could include:

- examples of volunteer or newcomer survey or exit interview questions;
- results of the volunteer or newcomer surveys or interviews (e.g., a summary of the issues that are raised) if they are available;
- reports on any evaluation that has been conducted of the group activity and any changes that have been made to the program in light of these evaluations.

DURING THE SITE VISIT:

3.2. Observation of the group activity

The second step is that one or two consultants from RealWorld Systems will observe the Host group activity in progress. (The consultants are Gillian Kerr, Anne Simard, and possibly Huamai Han).

As much as possible, the consultant will try to observe a regularly scheduled activity rather than create an event specifically to be observed.

The consultant will probably not play an active role in the activity, unless the agency wants us to make a brief presentation. We would like the Host coordinator or volunteers to introduce the consultant and explain her presence to the group participants. If you would like to discuss an alternative introduction format please let us know.

3.3. Focus group / interview process for volunteers and newcomers

The consultants hope to conduct three focus group/interviews while at the agency. These focus groups will include volunteers and newcomers who participate in the group activities that are being studied. A staff person from the agency is welcome to attend – in fact, it would be great if you could introduce us to the group and explain why we are there.

RealWorld Systems proposes three sessions:

- a. One session (hopefully 30 minutes) with clients of the Host group activity that has been observed

This session would take place immediately after the group activity and would include only those newcomers who participated at that activity.

- b. An open session for Host clients who are involved in group activities, regardless of whether or not they participated in the group observed. We will ask individual agencies for advice on how to invite clients; for example, we may talk to clients at an already-scheduled event rather than inviting clients to a special session. We are not aiming for a random or representative sample, since we are not trying to evaluate the program. Rather, we want to understand the group model. We hope to talk to at least 10 clients in total, though more would be fine.

The consultants will also interview the volunteers separately from the newcomers.

- c. One open session with group volunteers, hopefully including those who participated/facilitated in the Host group activity that we observed as well as other Host volunteers that are involved in the group model.

3.4. On-site review of agency documentation

Given the important role of volunteer management in Host, the consultants would like to review the volunteer management tools and supports (e.g., policies, training materials, booklet) developed by the agencies selected for site visits. The agency may be asked for permission (completely voluntary) to share some of these materials with other Host agencies.

We would encourage the agency to share whatever tools or resources it considers noteworthy or high-quality.

3.5. Follow-up interview and document review with Host staff

After observation of the group activity, review of documents, and interviews with volunteers and newcomers, we will follow up with Host staff to clarify, validate, or review findings prior to sharing the information we have gathered.

If you have any questions about this visit, or want to discuss the study, please feel free to contact any one of us:

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QUESTIONS FOR NEWCOMERS OF THE HOST GROUP ACTIVITY

These questions will be asked informally in an open-ended group meeting, and we may not use the exact wording or questions below. We would vary the wording according to the age and English skills of the people in the meeting. For example, school children might be asked, "What didn't you like?" instead of, "If you could change anything, what would it be?".

Satisfaction:

1. What did you like so far?
2. What are you hoping to get out of this group? (for new groups that are just starting up)
3. If you could change anything, what would it be?
4. Would you recommend this group to other newcomers like you? Why or why not?
5. How did you find out about the group? Were you encouraged to join?
6. Would you have preferred another kind of service?

Role and expectations of the group:

7. What did you contribute to the group? How would you like to contribute? How could you contribute more?
8. How would you like to support the agency or your community? [your school or your friends?]

Outcomes of participation:

9. What difference has this group made for you? Tell me a story about what difference it has made.
10. How can you tell that things have improved for you?
11. What has changed?
12. How is a group better than an individual meeting? Could you have achieved these same things with your individual Host volunteer?
13. How does the group help you to extend their networks?
14. Have you connected with anyone outside the group through the contacts made in the group? What kinds of people?
15. Do the volunteers play a role in introducing you to other people in the community?

Improvements and suggestions:

16. Do you like the location of your group? Would you prefer it to be somewhere else? Why?
17. What other kinds of groups would interest you?
18. How could the agency make this group better?

QUESTIONS FOR VOLUNTEERS OF THE HOST GROUP ACTIVITY
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3.6. Outcomes of the group:

1. How can you tell that the group activity is working? What do you look for?
2. What does success look like for newcomers in this group? What changes or improvements do you see?
3. Does this group approach work better for certain groups or types of newcomers? Who does it appeal to? Who can most benefit?
4. How is a group better than an individual meeting? Could you have achieved these same things with your individual Host newcomer?
5. How does the group help the newcomers extend their networks?
6. Do the newcomers connect with anyone outside the group through the contacts made in the group? What kinds of people?
7. Do you play a role in introducing newcomers to other people in the community?

Personal Outcomes:

8. What have you gained from volunteering in this group?
9. What has changed for you? Tell me a story about what difference it has made for you.
10. How would we know that this group offers a meaningful experience for volunteers?

Your role and responsibilities

11. Do you feel adequately trained and supported in your role? Why or why not?
12. What difficulties or challenges do you face in this volunteer role?
13. What would help you do your volunteer job better?
14. Any advice for the agency?

4. 2001 ENGLISH CONVERSATION CIRCLE GUIDELINES FROM CIC

Guidelines for English Conversation Circles in Ontario Region October 2001

The HOST Evaluation, completed in April 2001, revealed that a major reason for newcomers becoming involved in the HOST program is the opportunity to practice English speaking skills. CIC would like to incorporate English conversation circles into current HOST programming.

Definition of English Conversation Circles

English Conversation Circles exist as a resource for newcomers in the HOST program who wish to improve spoken English skills while simultaneously discussing topics of interest that may aid in their integration into Canadian society. Volunteers have the opportunity to learn about the diverse backgrounds of newcomers. Conversation Circles usually consist of 6-8 newcomers led by a volunteer.

Benefits of English Conversation Circles

- Benefits more newcomers since it is a group activity; especially useful in large urban areas where there is a shortage of volunteers
- Utilizes specialized volunteer skills if available
- Assures relevance to client since topics are normally client driven
- Encourages newcomers to practise English conversation in a relaxed informal atmosphere; there is often no time for practise in regular LINC classes and newcomers may be inhibited
- Allows Canadian volunteers to interact with broader a range of cultures

Timeframes and Size of English Conversation Circles

- One volunteer to a maximum of 8 newcomers
- Sessions should be a minimum of one hour, preferably two
- Circles can be held on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis according to demand.

Criteria for Volunteers leading Conversation Circles (aside from HOST program eligibility. e.g. must be permanent resident or Canadian Citizen)

- Must have lived in Canada 3 years
- Must be fluent in English and be able to communicate effectively
- Must be knowledgeable about Canada and life in Canada (customs, politics, etc.), as well as local area

Volunteer Responsibilities

Volunteers could be responsible for:

- inviting newcomers to sessions based on a list provided by the SPO
- scheduling sessions

- assisting with topic choice for next session
- ensuring newcomers are reminded of upcoming sessions.

Volunteers may have to do preparation (such as research topics), but conversation groups are not required to have formal curricula. Newcomers may choose to participate by offering to research topics of interest for discussion.

Newcomer Clients

Recent research has indicated that there are several newcomer groups that could be considered high needs. During this upcoming contract period, consideration should be given to targeting conversation circles and matches to the following groups:

- *youth aged 15-24*
- *seniors*
- *parents with young children*

For instance, some schools in Ontario have the SWIS (Settlement workers in Schools program). Those schools involved with SWIS may be useful for outreach and liaison. Another possible source of volunteers are high schools whose students are mandated to spend volunteer time in the community.

Statistical Definition of English Conversation Circles

Conversation Circles are a **group activity**, and do not result in matches as routinely described in the HOST program. It is clear, however, that newcomers benefit from attendance at this activity.

Each group session will be counted under a heading titled **Group Activity: English Conversation Circles** (e.g.) if 4 sessions are held in a one month period, they will be counted as 4 English Conversation circles. This means that sessions can be scheduled in cycles/ or year round; this will give more flexibility to agencies.

With respect to clients (newcomers), the total number of participants in attendance will be counted. Each client should be counted once. Only **new participants** should be counted at subsequent sessions. OASIS is seeking the total number of sessions held and total number of participants who benefited over a particular time period (usually contract duration). As long as a client attends a conversation circle once, they are counted as a participant. Note: a client should only be counted once during a fiscal year period (April to March).

Volunteers involved would be counted under the heading of host volunteers.

Alternative Models:

Service Providers may also take the opportunity to examine different models for the Conversation Circles, such as recruitment of organizations (such as faith institutions) that may be interested in providing a weekly venue for the sessions. In this instance, the organization would provide the volunteers, venue and organize refreshments. The main

function of the HOST Service Provider would be to recruit a willing organization and to visit the Conversation Circles to ensure that they are functioning well.

Other Considerations:

- Individual HOST matches are beneficial for clients and should still remain the primary focus of the organization's HOST program. English Conversation Circles should not be the **sole activity** in the organization's HOST program
- Where possible, the conversation circles should be client driven. Topics to be discussed should be chosen by newcomers or with their input. Conversation circles do not require a formalized curriculum, and newcomers may volunteer to assist with the organization of the session where feasible (such as providing topic research).
- Classes may be divided so that they are appropriate to the newcomers level of English where possible
- English Conversation Circles should not become language classes; they are not meant to replace Language Instruction for Newcomers to Canada(LINC).
- *The English conversation circle should be monitored at least once every 2 months by the HOST coordinator.*
- This activity should be reported as part of the narrative on the monthly SPO claim form.
- Exit surveys should be done by the SPO at the end of the match cycle, and a **summary of results** shared with CIC. Many SPOs already conduct exit surveys/evaluations of their activities. A sample survey will be available if requested.

At this point, no additional funding will be provided to deliver conversation circles. Your project officer will work with your organization on determining the amount of time it requires to organize this activity.

A conference call or meeting will be arranged in Spring 2002 with HOST Lead, HOST Coordinators, and settlement project officers to exchange best practices and challenges during the initial phase.

5. SUMMARY CHARTS OF HOST GROUP MODELS

The following charts are based on the information on the summary spreadsheet of Host Group Models that is available with this report. The spreadsheet identifies every agency offering group models, and gives detailed information on the following data elements. It was too large to be included in the body of this report.

Note that the spreadsheet may not be completely accurate. Even though agencies reviewed our data, many of the numbers were best estimates on the part of the interviewer and/or the Host staff.

Data Element	Description
Agency	Your agency's name
Agency City	The city that your agency is located in
Group Name	We included groups that fit the following criteria: * The group must serve at least some Host eligible clients * The group must use at least some Host resources (e.g., Host staff or volunteers or facilities) * The group must be active. We didn't count groups that you had not started yet, or that you have stopped offering, with the exception of regular summer programs
Group Model	Each group is assigned to one of the nine group service models described in the report. The possible choices are: * Socializing around language practice * Recreational/hobby groups * School buddies * Youth drop-ins * Community engagement * Language classes * Learning about Canada * Structured activities * Skills training/tutoring/homework clubs.
Program Running	(APPROXIMATELY) – Number of years that the program has been operating. If you are not sure, please make your best guess.
Partners	Other agencies or external programs that help to provide the group service. Partners are involved in actually working with or serving the volunteers or clients in the Host group activity. For example, Frontier College providing tutors to youth, or libraries that use Host groups as outreach for their own programs and encourage newcomers to participate.
Supporters	Other agencies or external programs that provide resources or special discounts to the Host group model, but do not participate in the provision of the service. For example, local newspapers that run free volunteer recruitment ads, or churches that rent out their basement without getting involved in the program.
Target Client Population	Does this Host group target any specific population? Who is it aimed at? Possible choices are: * Children or Youth Age 6-24 * Family * Specific Ethnocultural Group(s) (e.g., Latin Americans) * Refugees * Specific Length of Time in Canada (e.g., under 1 year)
Newcomer Status	What kinds of clients are accepted into the Host groups? Possible choices are: * Host-eligible newcomers * Host clients that are already in 1-1 matches * Other Newcomers (e.g., any newcomer who wants to participate including refugee claimants, international students, community members)
Other Attendees	Besides newcomers, who typically attends the group sessions? Possible choices are: * Host agency staff * Host volunteers * Other volunteers or agencies (e.g., Frontier College tutors, professionals, external speakers)
Approximate Ratio of Clients to Volunteers	If there are usually about 10 newcomers and 2 volunteers, the ratio would be 5:1. We made our best guess based on our interview, but please correct this if it is wrong.
Approximate Typical Group Size	How many participants generally attend, including volunteers
Approximate Typical	Times per week or per month

Meeting Frequency	
Approximate Meeting Duration (in hours)	
Estimated Total Hours for Each Participant	The number of hours that a typical group participant would spend in the group during a full fiscal year. For example, in one ECC, the typical participant might go for 10 weeks and spend a total of 20 hours (2 hours x 10 weeks). In another ECC, participants might go almost every week for a full year – about 80 to 100 hours. Please make your best guess.
Typical Meeting Location	Possible choices are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * University * Settlement or immigrant-serving agency (includes Host agency location) * Social service agency * Library * School or university * Place of worship * Social/recreational facility or community centre * Public space (e.g., parks, malls, restaurants, stadiums) * Individual homes * Formal event spaces e.g. hotel ballrooms
Relation to 1-1 Matches	Does the Host group have any relationship to the 1-to-1 matches? Possible choices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * S = Supports 1-1 matches; both volunteers and newcomers attend the groups together * W = Waiting list; Newcomers are invited to the group while they are waiting to be matched * M = Matching; Group encourages newcomers and volunteers to develop a 1-1 match * N = No relationship; Group has no formal link to the 1-1 matches
Primary Objective	This should be the main goal of the agency in providing this group, not necessarily the main objective of the newcomers. For example, youth may attend to play basketball, but the group is designed to develop the youths' social network. Possible choices are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * English practice * French practice * Social network development * Information and/or referral - accessing or learning about community resources * Welcoming, orientation to community and Canada Cultural exchange and rules for social interaction - e.g., accepted behaviour, holidays, raising hands to be heard * Specific skills development, e.g. computer skills
Secondary Objectives	Same choices as previous; you may choose two secondary objectives
Typical Activities	These should be listed in order of their frequency. For example, and should only be activities that are commonly done in the group. Possible choices are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Structured games and exercises * Discussion (on general or defined topics) * Role-playing (e.g., for conflict resolution) * Teaching specific skills (e.g., non-social, school topics like math, homework, computers, art) * Socializing (e.g., potlucks, special events) * Recreational * Field trips * Community engagement (e.g., designing Christmas floats, participating in art exhibit)
Typical Group Activity Leader	Possible choices are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Agency staff leads the group activity * One or two volunteers lead the group activity * Participants direct the group activities, possibly after a brief introduction by volunteer(s) or staff * Unstructured and undirected
Agenda Development	Possible choices are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Agenda is set by agency, either staff or lead volunteers (e.g., a retired teacher presents a structured curriculum and leads the group in language exercises) * Agenda is set by group participants at the beginning of the entire program (e.g., at the first meeting, the group decides on what issues to address in the next 10 weeks) * Agenda is set by group participants at the beginning of each session (e.g., in the first 10 minutes, the participants decide what topic to discuss, then break into small groups) * Agenda is unstated or not set (e.g., getting together in the park to play)
Commitment to Group	Possible choices are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Participants drop in with no expectation that they will attend each group meeting * Participants sign up for the entire session (e.g., 10 weeks) * Participants commit to the specific event (e.g., preparing a potluck dinner or designing a parade float)
Other Issues or Comments	

Figure 1: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Target Client Population

Figure 2: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Primary Objective

Figure 3: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Primary & Secondary Objectives

Figure 4: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Client to Volunteer Ratio

Figure 5: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Typical Hours Attendance Per Participant

Figure 6: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Group Meeting Leadership Role

Figure 7: HOST Group Models - Agenda Development

Figure 8: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Years Running

Figure 9: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Typical Meeting Location

Figure 10: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Target Client Population (2)

Figure 11: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Typical Meeting Frequency

HOST Group Model Breakdown by Participant Commitment to Group

Total Number of Active Host Group Models = 51

Figure 12: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Participant Commitment to Group

Figure 13: HOST Group Model Breakdown by Typical Primary Activity

6. SNAPSHOT OF HOST EVALUATION FORMS

The following are examples of evaluation forms used in the Host program among Ontario agencies, sampling just seven agencies. These forms are available on request from RealWorld Systems, and are examples of the kind of material that may be shared between service providers.

AGENCY	Type of evaluation form						
	Newcomer evaluation of Host program	Volunteer evaluation of Host program	Newcomer evaluation of Conversation Circles	Group activity evaluation	Other Group activity evaluation	Other Group activity evaluation	
Quinte United Immigrant Services	✓ (1 page)						
London Cross Cultural Learner Centre			✓ (1 page)				
Centre francophone de Toronto		✓ (2 pages)					
Catholic Community Services of York Region	✓ (1 page)	✓ (1 page)					
Multicultural Council of Windsor and Essex County	✓ Client follow-up form (2 pages)	✓ Follow-up questionnaire for volunteers (2 pages)	✓ Conversation Circle evaluation (1 page)	✓ Circle of friends evaluation (2 pages)	✓ SAC survey feedback form (1 page)		

	Client exit interview (2 pages)	Volunteer exit interview (2 pages)					
KW YMCA	✓ End-of-match newcomer survey (2 pages)	✓ End-of-match volunteer survey (1 page)	✓ Participant evaluation (ESL Café) (2 pages)	✓ YMCA School host workshop evaluation (1 page)	✓ YMCA School host program evaluation (2 pages)	✓ YMCA School host friends club (1 page)	
CultureLink	✓ Host newcomer evaluation 2003 (3 pages)	✓ Host volunteer evaluation 2003 (3 pages)					

8. HOST LOGIC MODEL

Host Logic Model

7. SPREADSHEET WITH DESCRIPTION OF HOST GROUPS

This file requires Microsoft Excel to open. It is quite large, so you may want to 'hide' rows and columns that you don't want to read so that the spreadsheet can be printed out more easily.

The data elements that it collects are described in Section 6: Summary Charts of Host Group Models, above.

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Settings\Gillian Kerr*